

Laser-induced creation of coherent V2 centers in bulk-grown silicon carbide

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Solid-state spin defects are promising qubits for quantum network nodes. A key challenge towards larger networks is creating defects with high yield into nanophotonic devices, while maintaining good optical and spin properties. Here, we demonstrate the creation of V2 centers in nanopillars fabricated from commercial bulk-grown 4H-silicon carbide using a pulsed above-bandgap (UV) laser. We observe an eleven-fold increase in the V2 center occurrence after UV laser illumination. These laser-induced V2 centers exhibit narrow optical linewidths and spectral diffusion rates comparable to naturally occurring V2 centers in nanopillars of the same material. Furthermore, we measure a spin coherence time of $T_2^{\text{DD}} = 3.6(3)$ ms under dynamical decoupling, consistent with dephasing by the nuclear-spin bath. This demonstration of the in-situ, post-fabrication generation of coherent V2 centers in nanostructures in widely available bulk-grown 4H-SiC, shows the potential for above-bandgap laser illumination for scalable defect creation in integrated photonic devices.

INTRODUCTION

Solid-state spin defects provide promising qubits for quantum networks, as they combine high-fidelity spin-photon entanglement with access to nuclear spins with long coherence times¹⁻³. Their compatibility with integrated photonics offers a scalable path towards large-scale quantum networks⁴⁻⁶. A central challenge is the deterministic placement of defects within sub-wavelength nanophotonic structures while preserving good optical and spin coherence⁷⁻¹⁰.

Silicon carbide (4H-SiC) hosts a variety of optically active spin defects¹⁰⁻²⁰. The negatively charged single k-site silicon vacancy center (V2) is a promising candidate as long spin coherence times and near-lifetime-limited optical transitions, required for remote entanglement generation, have been demonstrated in nanophotonic devices²¹⁻²³.

Several methods have successfully demonstrated the creation of localised single V2 centers, such as masked He⁺ ion implantation^{21,24} and focused ion beam (FIB) implantation²⁵⁻²⁷, including with in-situ monitoring²⁸. Pulsed-laser writing is a compelling alternative that provides defect creation with good spatial precision, after device fabrication²⁹⁻³². In addition, laser writing is compatible with in-situ monitoring²⁹, potentially enabling deterministic defect creation. Pioneering experiments in 4H-SiC have shown that below-bandgap laser writing can create colour centers in bulk³¹⁻³³, while above-bandgap laser writing has further enabled the creation of V2 centers in 1D nanophotonic crystal cavities³⁰.

However, the optical and spin coherence of single laser-written defects in 4H-SiC, which are essential for many quantum applications, has thus far remained unexplored.

Here, we demonstrate laser-induced creation of V2 centers in nanopillars with preserved optical and spin coherence. We use an above-bandgap laser and commercial bulk-grown High-Purity Semi-Insulating (HPSI) 4H-SiC, widely available as 4-6 inch wafers.

We first identify the pulse energy window that enables defect formation without inducing surface amorphisation. Subsequently, we show the creation of single laser-induced V2 centers and characterise their optical properties. We show near-lifetime-limited optical linewidths and slow spectral diffusion rates, similar to naturally occurring V2 centers in the same type of nanopillars. Finally, we demonstrate long electron-spin coherence times (up to 3.6(3) ms) for laser-induced V2 centers, similar to values reported in high-quality epitaxial 4H-SiC^{11,34}. The demonstration of spatially selective defect creation after device fabrication, with good optical and spin coherence in nano-structures made of commercial bulk-grown wafers, indicates that above-bandgap pulsed-laser illumination is a promising route towards scalable generation of coherent V2 centers in 4H-SiC devices.

RESULTS

Laser-induced amorphization

We use an above-bandgap (337 nm, 3.68 eV) pulsed (3 ns) laser (similar as Day *et al.*³⁰) focussed on the sample via a 0.7 NA objective and investigate single-pulse defect creation in HPSI 4H-SiC with a bandgap of 3.26 eV³⁵ (Fig. 1a,b). Given the high efficiency of electron-hole pair generation at above-bandgap excitation, the material is susceptible to irreversible damage under intense irradiation³⁰. To mitigate this, we first determine the laser-induced amorphization threshold (LIAT)^{36,37} for both nanopillars and bulk HPSI 4H-SiC. This is achieved by exposing one hundred discrete

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FIG. 1. **Laser-induced defect creation using an above-bandgap pulsed laser.** **a)** Schematic of the laser-induced creation and detection of defects in HPSI 4H-SiC. A 0.7 NA objective focuses an above-bandgap (337 nm) pulsed (3 ns) laser onto the center of the nanopillar to create defects. For imaging, we use a 0.9 NA objective and a 785 nm laser for off-resonant excitation. **b)** Scanning electron microscopy image of the HPSI amorphized nanopillars that were exposed to a single UV pulse with energies higher than the LIAT ($0.28 \mu\text{J}$). The nanopillars are $\sim 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter and $\sim 4 \mu\text{m}$ spaced from center to center. **c)** Amorphisation statistics of nanopillars using a single pulse. For each pulse energy, one hundred nanopillars were each illuminated with a single pulse, and the percentage of nanopillars that showed visible damage is indicated on the y-axis. Blue dots indicate $0.18 \mu\text{J}$ and $0.24 \mu\text{J}$, which are used for Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. See Fig. S1 for SEM pictures of amorphisation. **d)** 2D PL scans before and after a single UV pulse of $0.24 \mu\text{J}$ at each pillar. The counts for both measurements were corrected to have the same background counts in bulk close to the nanopillars (before counts $\times 1.524$, and after counts $\times 0.656$, see Supplementary Note 3 for correction method). **e)** Fluorescence saturation measurements before and after a single UV pulse of $0.24 \mu\text{J}$ on the same pillar.

spots per pulse energy. After UV illumination, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is used to quantify the number of sites exhibiting resolvable surface amorphization (see Supplementary Note 1). We note that our analysis is limited to SEM-detectable surface amorphization, which excludes sub-surface lattice damage.

Despite being limited to surface-level observations, our analysis enables the identification of three distinct regimes: unresolvable, probabilistic amorphization, and deterministic amorphization, observed in both the nanopillars (Fig. 1c) and bulk material (Supplementary Note 1). We find that the LIAT for nanopillars ($> 0.28 \mu\text{J}$) is lower compared to bulk ($> 0.32 \mu\text{J}$), showing that it is dependent on the nanophotonic structure (consistent with previous studies³⁸).

Laser-induced defect creation

With the LIAT determined, we verify that defect creation is possible at energies below this threshold. We perform off-resonant (785 nm) 2D photoluminescence (PL) scans before and after a single UV laser pulse for pulse energies below the LIAT, employing a 0.9 NA objective to improve collection efficiency (Supplementary Note 2). An example of one of these 2D PL scans can be found in Fig. 1d. For pulse energies $\geq 0.16 \mu\text{J}$, the 2D PL scans show an increase in PL for nearly all nanopillars (see Supplementary Note 3), indicating sub-surface lattice deformation or laser-induced defect generation³⁹. Next, we perform fluorescence saturation measurements under off-resonant laser excitation on each individual nanopillar. These measurements reveal early saturation effects, associated with quantum-defect emission, for UV pulse energies $\geq 0.16 \mu\text{J}$, see Supplementary Note 4.

To further investigate the number of defects generated by a single UV pulse, we perform fluorescence saturation

measurements on an additional 64 nanopillars before and after a single 0.18 μJ UV pulse (low-probability regime), and on 64 nanopillars exposed to a 0.24 μJ pulse (higher-probability regime). An example of a nanopillar fluorescence saturation measurement before and after a single pulse can be seen in Fig. 1e.

V2 concentration

To determine whether the observed increase in PL arises from the presence of V2 centers, we search for the characteristic zero-phonon line emission, corresponding to the A1 and A2 optical transitions, through Photoluminescence Excitation spectroscopy (PLE) spectra at 4 K^{17,40}. The number of naturally occurring V2 centers is then compared with the number after a single UV pulse of 0.18 μJ or 0.24 μJ . We fit all PLE spectra (see Methods and Supplementary Note 5) and compare the frequencies and amplitudes of the fitted peaks (example of PLE in Fig. 2a). Evaluating the percentage of V2 centers with peak amplitudes above a certain threshold reveals a significantly larger number of high-count-rate V2 centers in UV-exposed nanopillars (see Fig. 2b). Relative to the brightest V2 center in the non-exposed nanopillars (0.76(2) kHz), nanopillars exposed to a 0.18 μJ or 0.24 μJ UV pulse contain roughly three and eleven times more V2 centers that reach or exceed this brightness, respectively. Furthermore, the brightest V2 center found in the UV-exposed nanopillars has a count rate of 2.11(4) kHz, approximately a factor of 2.8 higher than the brightest emitter in the non-exposed nanopillars.

Because weak background emission can originate from defects outside the nanopillars, we restrict our analysis to V2 centers with a PLE amplitude above 0.3 kHz (dotted line, Fig. 2a,b). This threshold ensures that only bright, well-collected V2 centers (most likely located near the nanopillar center, see Supplementary Note 2) are included.

Using the 0.3 kHz threshold, we find that the frequencies of the V2 centers in the UV-exposed nanopillars follow the same ensemble inhomogeneous distribution as the natural V2 center population (Fig. 2c). This suggests that the UV pulse does not introduce significant strain or amorphisation in the vicinity of the laser-induced V2 centers^{22,41,42}. Furthermore, we quantify the probability of inducing only one bright V2 center for the two UV pulse energies (Fig. 2d). After a single 0.18 μJ pulse, $\sim 23\%$ of the nanopillars contain one bright V2 center, increasing to $\sim 33\%$ for 0.24 μJ . For comparison, this is observed in only $\sim 6\%$ of non-exposed nanopillars.

These results show that the UV-pulse strongly increases the number of V2 centers, even though the exact origin of each V2 center, whether created by the UV-pulse or naturally present, cannot be determined unambiguously. As we will show below, the optical properties of V2 centers with and without UV illumination are very similar, so this ambiguity does not affect the conclusion

that the UV pulse induces high-quality V2 centers. In the remainder of this work, we will therefore refer to V2 centers in UV-exposed nanopillars as laser-induced V2 centers and in non-exposed nanopillars as natural V2 centers.

V2 optical properties

Next, we characterise the optical properties of the laser-induced V2 centers and compare them to natural V2 centers using the check-probe spectroscopy methodology of van de Stolpe *et al.*²³. We characterised 24 individual V2 centers, including 3 natural (circles in Fig. 3a,b) and 21 laser-induced centers. Among the laser-induced centers, 10 were exposed to a single UV pulse with an energy of 0.18 μJ (squares), while 11 were exposed to a single pulse with an energy of 0.24 μJ (triangles).

The measured spectral diffusion rates under resonant and off-resonant excitation are shown in Fig. 3a,b. This reveals a 3-4 orders-of-magnitude difference in spectral diffusion between resonant and off-resonant laser light, consistent with previous work²³. Additionally, we observe a significant spread in spectral diffusion rates, indicating that each V2 center experiences a distinct local charge environment. Importantly, we find no significant difference in the spectral diffusion rates between laser-induced and natural V2 centers; the two groups exhibit similar overall distributions. This suggests that the single UV pulse does not substantially alter the effective local charge environment, and that the impurities of the HPSI material or the embedding in a nanopillar, are still the main cause of spectral diffusion⁴². Within the distribution of spectral diffusion constants (γ_d) for laser-induced V2 centers, some V2 centers remain particularly stable, exhibiting low γ_d even under off-resonant excitation (green and red markers in Fig. 3a,b).

We perform two additional types of photoluminescence excitation (PLE) measurements. First, we observe the spectral wandering (Fig. 3c) by scanning a resonant laser continuously whilst applying microwaves; second, we use a check-probe type PLE on the A1 transition to approximate the homogeneous linewidth (Fig. 3d)²³. By sweeping the threshold for the check-probe PLE, we can minimize the residual broadening due to imperfect initialisation and compare this homogeneous linewidth to the lifetime-limited linewidth (see Supplementary Note 7). We find linewidths satisfying $1 \leq \Gamma/\Gamma_{lifetime} \leq 4$ for all measured V2 centers, indicating that there is still some broadening (either residual (in)homogeneous broadening, or power broadening). The linewidths for the natural V2 centers are similar to the laser-induced V2 centers, indicating that the UV pulse does not significantly lower the optical coherence of the V2 centers and, importantly, are compatible with remote entanglement generation under modest time filtering⁴³.

FIG. 2. **Photoluminescence Excitation spectroscopy (PLE) and number of V2 centers.** **a)** Single PLE of a nanopillar with three V2 centers passing a threshold (dashed grey line) at 0.3 kHz. Laser frequency is offset from 327.112 THz. Inset shows the experimental sequence, green indicates an off-resonant (repump) pulse (10 μs, 10 μW), red indicates a single resonant laser (2 ms, 100 nW). Grey indicates microwaves (MW) at (70 MHz) to counteract spin pumping. **b)** Percentage of V2 centers whose fitted peak amplitude exceeds the count-rate threshold, shown separately for nanopillars exposed to a UV pulse (0.18 μJ and 0.24 μJ) and those left unexposed; in each condition, $n = 64$ nanopillars are examined. We find a maximum count rate for the non-exposed V2 center of 0.76 kHz. For this threshold, we also observe three and eleven times more V2 centers with the same or higher count rate at UV laser powers of 0.18 μJ and 0.24 μJ, respectively. **c)** Ensemble inhomogeneous distribution of all V2 centers in unexposed nanopillars (bottom grey bars). A Gaussian fit yields a FWHM of the inhomogeneous distribution of 22(1) GHz. The blue bars indicate the frequencies of the V2 centers in the UV-exposed nanopillars that pass the threshold of 0.3 kHz (this threshold sets a cut-off to suppress bulk-V2 contributions, also indicated by the dotted line in b)). The black dashed line shows the (scaled) Gaussian fit of the unexposed inhomogeneous distribution as a guide to the eye. **d)** Number of nanopillars that contain either 0, 1, 2, or 3 V2 centers that pass the 0.3 kHz threshold. Nanopillars exposed to the UV laser are shown in shades of blue, while natural (unexposed) V2 centers are shown in shades of grey. The numbers inside the bars show how many pillars contain that specific number of V2 centers.

V2 electron-spin properties

In addition to optical coherence, the electron spin coherence is a crucial component for utilising laser-induced V2 centers in sensing, quantum information processing, and quantum network applications. We investigate the spin properties of two single laser-induced V2 centers, which exhibits relatively low spectral diffusion (γ_d) under both resonant and off-resonant excitation (pillar 9 and 14; see Fig. S7 for location details, Fig. S18 for optical properties of V2 center in pillar 9, Fig. 3c,d for optical properties of V2 center in pillar 14 and Fig. S22 for spin properties of V2 center in pillar 14). Note that this optical selection might already introduce a bias in the electron spin environment and, thus, potentially in the electron spin coherence.

First, we operate at a magnetic field of ~ 40 G. This ensures that the Kramers degeneracy within the $\pm \frac{1}{2}$ and $\pm \frac{3}{2}$ spin eigenstates is lifted, and that the ground or ex-

cited state level crossings are sufficiently detuned^{42,44,45}. Fig. 4a shows Rabi oscillations for driving the ground state $|m_s = +\frac{1}{2}\rangle \leftrightarrow |m_s = +\frac{3}{2}\rangle$ transition of the V2 center found in pillar 9. On the same V2 center, we perform electron spin resonance (ESR), see Fig. 4b (details of the sequence can be found in Supplementary Note 9). ESR reveals a strongly coupled nuclear spin, with a hyperfine coupling of 2.19(5) MHz. This coupling is consistent with either a coupled ^{13}C or ^{29}Si nuclear spin as previously observed and reported⁴⁶, and accounts for the detuning visible in the Rabi chevron pattern (Fig. 4a and Supplementary Note 9). We perform Ramsey measurements to extract the spin-dephasing time T_2^* , finding $T_2^* = 0.9(1)$ μs.

Next, we operate at a higher magnetic field (~ 1300 G) to suppress decoherence from anisotropic hyperfine interactions with the spin bath. We perform Hahn-echo and dynamical decoupling (DD) measurements on the V2 center in pillar 14, which has no strongly coupled nuclear spins. We measure a Hahn-echo coherence time

FIG. 3. **V2 optical properties and spectral diffusion.** **a)** Fitted spectral diffusion constant under off-resonant excitation for natural V2 centers (circles) and laser-induced V2 centers (squares and triangles, 0.18 μJ and 0.24 μJ respectively). We extract γ_d using the methodology described in van de Stolpe *et al.*²³, assuming a homogeneous linewidth (FWHM) of 36 MHz. Because the fitted γ_d depends on this homogeneous linewidth (see Supplementary Note 6), and this linewidth was not measured for each individual V2 center, we indicate the spread in γ_d for a plausible range of linewidths ($1 \leq \Gamma/\Gamma_{\text{lifetime}} \leq 3$, see Supplementary Note 7). γ_d of the red square indicates the same V2 center as the green square in b) and data in c) and d). **b)** Fitted spectral diffusion constants under resonant excitation. **c)** Scanning laser PLE over 5 minutes of the V2 center highlighted in a) and b) (Pillar 14, Fig. S7). The laser is on for a total of 334 ms per scan with a power at the objective of 20 nW. **d)** Check-Probe PLE (see van de Stolpe *et al.*²³ for methodology) with FWHM = 52(4) MHz indicating similar optical linewidth ($\Gamma/\Gamma_{\text{lifetime}} = 2.21(4)$, see Fig. S16) as natural V2 centers in this material (see Fig. S15). Check-probe PLE was performed at a magnetic field of ~ 20 G aligned along the crystal c-axis.

of $T_2^{\text{Hahn}} = 0.49(2)$ ms and extend the coherence up to $T_2^{\text{DD}} = 3.6(3)$ ms using two consecutive XY8 sequences (Fig. 4d).

The T_2^{DD} values display a power-law dependence on the number of decoupling pulses, with a fitted exponent of $\alpha = 0.73(4)$. This is slightly higher than the $\alpha = 2/3$ scaling associated with a Lorentzian noise spectrum ($\sim \frac{1}{\omega^2}$), characteristic of Ornstein-Uhlenbeck dynamics⁴⁷, indicating a slight deviation from a single-Lorentzian noise spectrum toward lower frequency noise⁴⁸. Despite the relatively high nitrogen concentration of ($\sim 1.1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, see Methods) our T_2 and T_2^{Hahn} are comparable to values reported for natural-isotope-abundance epitaxially grown 4H-SiC with doping levels two orders of magnitude lower^{11,34,49–52}. This suggests that neither the doping level nor the laser-writing method limits the spin coherence. These results show that commercially available wafers combined with laser-induced defect creation might provide a viable path towards quantum technologies based on colour centers in 4H-SiC.

DISCUSSION

In this work, we studied the creation of laser-induced V2 centers in 4H-SiC nanopillars in bulk-grown SiC. We observe narrow optical linewidths that are compatible with remote entanglement generation⁴³, and long electron-spin coherence times consistent with dephasing by the nuclear spin bath¹¹, although potential contributions from electron spin impurities cannot be excluded.

Looking forward, while here we focus on the formation of V2 centers in bulk-grown 4H-SiC wafers, the methods employed here can potentially be extended to high-quality, isotopically engineered, epitaxially grown 4H-SiC^{53–57}, and as well to other defect centers, such as V1 centers (h-site V_{Si}^-)⁴⁰, divacancies¹⁴, and non-native atom-related complexes like NV centers¹⁵. A systematic exploration of defect formation, density, and properties using above-bandgap laser writing, across different irradiation conditions and writing parameters, can enable deeper insight into the underlying material science and the mechanisms of defect creation, including potential local annealing or activation effects⁵⁸, in different types of SiC and nanostructures.

Additionally, monitoring the photoluminescence between laser pulses might enable the deterministic creation

FIG. 4. **Electron spin properties.** **a)** Rabi chevron pattern from the V2 center in pillar 9. Details on the measurement sequence and normalisation procedure are elaborated in [Supplementary Note 9](#). **b)** Electron-spin-resonance of the same V2 center revealing a strongly coupled nuclear spin with hyperfine splitting of 2.19(5) MHz (red line). The two solid vertical lines indicate the fitted frequencies from the Ramsey measurement, matching the ESR frequencies. **c)** Detuned Ramsey measurement on the same V2 center with $f_{MW} = 181.8$ MHz. Red line indicates a fit to an oscillation with two frequency components and a Gaussian decay, which translates to a hyperfine splitting of $f_{HF} = 2.08(7)$ MHz, and $T_2^* = 0.9(1)$ μ s. **d)** Scaled Hahn-echo ($N = 1$) and dynamical decoupling ($N = 2$ to $N = 16$) measurements on the V2 center in pillar 14 (Fig. S7) with no (resolvable) strongly coupled nuclear spin (see Fig. S22 for Chevron, ESR and Ramsey) at a magnetic field of ~ 1300 G. We find a $T_2^{\text{Hahn}} = 0.49(2)$ ms and extend the coherence time to $T_2^{\text{DD}} = 3.6(3)$ ms with two XY8 sequences. The inset shows T_2 as a function of the number of π -pulses N , fitted to a power function $T_2 = \beta \cdot N^\alpha$ (excluding Hahn-echo) from which we extract $\alpha = 0.73(4)$ and $\beta = 0.46(4)$ ms.

of a desired number of defects²⁹. Large-scale fabrication methods, such as Silicon-Carbide-on-Insulator⁵ or angled etching¹⁰, would open the door to complex integrated nanophotonic structures, including photonic crystal cavities. Together with the laser-induced creation of high-quality V2-centers in commercial bulk-grown SiC wafers presented here, this combination might enable a path towards efficient, high-quality defect creation in scalable quantum devices.

METHODS

Sample preparation

The sample was diced directly from a 6-inch High-Purity Semi-Insulating (HPSI) wafer obtained from Wolf-speed (model type W4TRG0R-N-0200). We note that the HPSI terminology originates from the silicon carbide electronics industry. In the quantum technology context considered here, this material has a significant amount of residual impurities (order $\sim 10^{15}$ cm^{-3} according to Son et al.³⁵) and is hence considered low material

quality with respect to a concentration of $\sim 10^{13}$ cm^{-3} typical for epitaxially grown layers on the c -axis of silicon carbide^{22,40}. On a different sample, diced from a wafer of the same model type, secondary-ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) determined the nitrogen donor concentration as $[N] = 1.1 \times 10^{15}$ cm^{-3} . In addition to intrinsic silicon vacancies, additional silicon vacancies were generated in this sample through a previous (unrelated) 2 MeV electron irradiation with a fluence of 2×10^{13} cm^{-2} . The sample was annealed at 600 °C for 30 min in an Argon atmosphere. To enhance the optical collection efficiency and mitigate the unfavourable V2 dipole orientation for confocal access along the SiC growth axis (c -axis), we utilize nanopillars. Nanopillar fabrication begins with sputtering an aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) mask on the SiC substrate, followed by spinning and patterning of AR-P 6200 e-beam resist (Allresist GmbH). The resist pattern is transferred into the Al_2O_3 using inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE) with a BCl_3/Cl_2 plasma. Afterwards, the pattern is etched into the SiC using ICP-RIE and an SF_6/O_2 plasma. After ICP-RIE, the remaining Al_2O_3 was removed with hydrofluoric acid.

Pulsed UV experiment

To determine the LIAT for bulk material, we define a grid of 100 spots (10 by 10) for each pulse energy. To avoid spatial and temporal biasing (e.g., alignment or temperature drifts), the pulse energies are varied in a randomized order and calibrated before each measurement. All spots are positioned within a region where alignment artifacts are negligible. The z-position of the objective is fine-tuned by scanning through different heights while applying a pulse energy slightly above the LIAT. We then use the z position that produces the largest amorphization on the surface (see Supplementary Note 1).

The same procedure is used to determine the LIAT for nanopillars, with the grid consisting of 4 by 25 individual structures. The measurement process is fully automated, involving piezo movement of the objective and a single UV pulse. Due to grid interpolation and piezo positioner hysteresis, the UV pulse may not always focus in the exact center of each nanopillar. While this misalignment has minimal effect on the LIAT determination, it can slightly influence the resulting concentration of V2 centers.

Automated PLE V2 selection

We measure PLE spectra on 192 nanopillars and fit them automatically. We apply microwaves to the V2 centers using a bondwire ($\sim 20\ \mu\text{m}$ to $50\ \mu\text{m}$ away from the laser-induced V2 centers) to efficiently counter spin-pumping.

For the non-UV-exposed and UV-exposed nanopillars, we perform the following measurement sequence.

1. Optimize the x,y,z position of the focal point to maximize the amount of counts under off-resonant excitation for each nanopillar.
2. Perform photoluminescence excitation (PLE) measurement by scanning a resonant laser over 60 GHz (while continuously applying microwaves at 70 MHz) centered around the observed inhomogeneous distribution of V2 centers.
3. Fit a Voigt profile to all observed peaks in the PLE spectra and store the center frequency and amplitude of the fit. To avoid double counting (A1 and A2 transition of a single V2 center) and fitting errors, we set the additional constraints to the fit: distance between fitted peaks $> 2\ \text{GHz}$ and the FWHM of the fit should be larger than 50 MHz and lower than 3000 MHz and have a minimal count rate of 0.03 kHz.

Experimental setup

All room temperature experiments are performed using a home-built confocal microscopy setup. We use a 3 ns pulsed UV (337 nm) laser (Lasertechnik Berlin, MNL103-LD) together with a 0.7 NA objective (LUCPLFLN60X) for defect formation experiments. For PL measurements, the objective is switched to a 0.9 NA objective (Olympus MPLFLN100X). The UV excitation path is separated from the V2 excitation and collection pathway using a dichroic mirror (Semrock Di01-R355). V2 centers are repumped with a 785 nm laser (Cobolt 06-MLD785), and the resulting photoluminescence is filtered through an 830 nm long-pass filter (Semrock BLP01-830R-25) before being detected by superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs, Single Quantum).

Low-temperature experiments are performed using a home-built confocal microscopy setup at 4K (Montana Instruments S100). The NIR lasers (Toptica DL Pro and the Spectra-Physics Velocity TLB-6718-P) are frequency-locked to a wavemeter (HF-Angstrom WS/U-10U) and their power is modulated by acousto-optic modulators (G&H SF05958). A wavelength division multiplexer (OZ Optics) combines the 785 nm repump (Cobolt 06-MLD785) and NIR laser light, after which it is focused onto the sample using a fast-steering mirror (Newport FSM-300) and a movable, room temperature objective (Olympus MPLFLN 100X), which is kept at a vacuum and is thermally isolated by a heat shield. A 90:10 beam splitter that directs the laser light into the objective, allows V2 center phonon-sideband emission to pass through, to be detected on a superconducting nanowire single photon detector (SNSPD, Single Quantum, filtered by a Semrock FF01-937/LP-25 long pass filter at a slight angle). Alternatively, the emission can be directed to a spectrometer (Princeton Instruments Iso-Plane 81) and filtered by an 830 nm long-pass filter (Semrock BLP01-830R-25). Microwave pulses are generated by an arbitrary-waveform generator (Zurich Instruments HDAWG8) and an RF source (R&S SGS100A SGMA RF source), amplified (Mini-circuits LZY-22+ or ZHL-15W-422-S+), and delivered with a bond-wire drawn across the sample. The coarse-time scheduling (1 μs resolution) of the experiments is managed by a microcontroller (ADwin Pro II). For a schematic of the room-temperature and low-temperature setups, see Supplementary Note 11. All data was taken using the QMI Python package⁵⁹.

Magnetic field

For the check-probe PLE in Fig. 3d and spin coherence measurements Fig. 4a,b,c, we apply a low magnetic field along the defect symmetry axis (c-axis) using a permanent neodymium magnet outside the cryostat. For the check-probe PLE, we used a magnetic field of approximately $\sim 20\ \text{G}$, and for the spin coherence measurements, we applied a magnetic field of approximately $\sim 40\ \text{G}$ so

that the $|m_s = +\frac{1}{2}\rangle \leftrightarrow |m_s = +\frac{3}{2}\rangle$ transition is around 181.8 MHz. The magnetic field was aligned by applying the sequence depicted in the inset of Fig. 2a without applying MW pulses. We set f_1 to be resonant with the A2 transition and monitor the average photoluminescence (f_1 pulse duration is 2 ms). A (slightly) misaligned field causes spin-mixing between the $m_s = \pm\frac{3}{2}$ and $m_s = \pm\frac{1}{2}$ subspace, which increases the detected signal. Minimising the photoluminescence thus optimises the field alignment along the symmetry axis.

For the T_2^{DD} in Fig. 4d we apply a magnetic field of ~ 1300 G using a permanent neodymium magnet just behind the sample. We place 3 external magnets outside the cryostat on motorized stages to align the magnetic field as described previously.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All data underlying the study will be made available on the open 4TU data server.

CODE AVAILABILITY

Code used to operate the experiments is available on request.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

LJF, GMT and RK performed the room temperature creation and detection experiments. GMT and RK performed the amorphisation threshold measurements. GMT designed and fabricated the sample. LJF, YH, and TM performed the low-temperature optical and spin property measurements. GvdS, SJH, LJF, GMT, RK, TD, and AD built the experimental apparatus. LJF, GMT, RK, YH and THT analysed the data. LJF, GMT, YH and THT wrote the manuscript with input from all authors. THT supervised the project.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Supplementary Information for Laser-induced creation of coherent V2 centers in bulk-grown silicon carbide

Supplementary Note 1. Laser-induced amorphisation threshold

Due to the efficient generation of electron-hole pairs using an above-bandgap laser, linear photo-ionization can generate a high density of free electrons. This can lead to the formation of a highly ionised plasma, potentially resulting in material damage^{36,60,61}. Given the fixed pulse duration of 3 ns, we systematically vary the pulse energy of single-shot exposures to determine the damage threshold. This threshold defines the upper bound of pulse energy used in subsequent investigations, referred to as the laser-induced amorphisation threshold (LIAT). The procedure is applied to both bulk 4H-SiC and nanostructured pillars (diameter $\sim 1.2\ \mu\text{m}$, height $\sim 1\ \mu\text{m}$) and followed by SEM inspection, see Fig. S1a-f.

Figure S1. **SEM of LIAT for bulk and nanopillars.** **a)** Bulk experiment with single pulse energy of $0.20\ \mu\text{J}$, of a grid of 100 spots with no visible amorphisation. **b)** Bulk experiment with single pulse energy of $0.38\ \mu\text{J}$ with probabilistic (80%) amorphisation. **c)** Bulk experiment with single pulse energy of $0.40\ \mu\text{J}$ with 100% amorphisation. **d)** Nanopillar experiment with single pulse energy of $0.24\ \mu\text{J}$ of a grid of 100 spots with no visible amorphisation. **e)** Nanopillar experiment with single pulse energy of $0.3\ \mu\text{J}$ with probabilistic (46%) amorphisation. **f)** Nanopillar experiment with single pulse energy of $0.34\ \mu\text{J}$ with 100% amorphisation. **g)** The number of damaged sites for each pulse energy, for both bulk and nanopillars. **h)** Example of the focusing procedure of the UV laser. For each row, the z-position is slightly adjusted to compare the surface-damage diameter. In all the SEM images, the white bar indicates $5\ \mu\text{m}$.

Following SEM analysis, the number of damaged sites was quantified and plotted as a function of pulse energy

(Fig. S1g), revealing the energy dependence of laser-induced damage thresholds across different surface morphologies. A distinctly non-linear response is observed in both the bulk material and the nanopillars. As we do not focus on the probabilistic armorphization regime, we do not investigate this further.

Prior to each pulse-energy configuration, the UV laser focus was optimised on the substrate surface by adjusting the objective's z-axis, while using high-energy UV pulses of 0.45 μJ , to maintain consistent exposure parameters. As can be seen in Fig. S1h, the second row exhibits the largest surface-damage diameters, which we attribute to optimal focusing of the UV laser at the substrate surface during the experiment.

Supplementary Note 2. Simulated collection efficiency

Figure S2. **Simulated collection efficiency for nanopillars.** **a)** Geometry used to simulate the V2 center ZPL emission pattern in nanopillars using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6. 2D axis-symmetry is applied to reduce computational time. The green area is specified as 4H-SiC (62 : $\hat{\Gamma}\pm$ -SiC; $n(o)$ 0.488-1.064 μm), the blue area is specified as air, and the outer grey area is defined as a perfectly matched layer. In the center of the nanopillar, we place an artificial copper antenna to emulate the V2 center ZPL emission. **b)** The emission pattern of the V2 center in a nanopillar with dimensions as indicated with the black cross in **c**. For visualization purposes, the colour scale has been saturated to enhance the contrast and reveal the underlying emission pattern. **c),d)** The calculated collection efficiency for various nanopillar diameters and heights with a 0.7 and 0.9 NA objective, respectively.

The perpendicular optical dipole orientation of the V2 defect with respect to the surface (in c-plane 4H-SiC) limits the collection efficiency through an objective positioned above the sample. Nanopillars are an effective way to alleviate this limitation. To simulate the effects of a nanopillar structure, we use the 2D-axisymmetric electromagnetic waves, frequency-domain physics interface of COMSOL Multiphysics 5.6. Fig. S2a illustrates the geometry used. The green region is specified as 4H-SiC (Singh et al. 1971: $\hat{\Gamma}\pm$ -SiC; $n(o)$ 0.488-1.064 μm), the blue region is air, and the outer grey area is a perfectly matched layer. In the center of the nanopillar, an artificial copper antenna models the optical emission of a V2 defect, with a single frequency emission corresponding to the ZPL transition. The emission of a V2 defect in a nanopillar (dimensions indicated with the black cross in Fig. S2c) are shown in Fig. S2b. The collection efficiencies in Fig. S2c,d are calculated with:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{\text{objective}}}{P_{\text{tot}}}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

with P_{tot} being the total power emitted by the artificial antenna and P_{obj} the power directed towards the objective, calculated as:

$$P_{\text{obj}} = \int_0^{\sin^{-1}(\text{NA})} P_{\text{boundary}}(\theta) d\theta, \quad (\text{S2})$$

where P_{boundary} is the power normal to the boundary surface and $\text{NA} = 0.7$ and $\text{NA} = 0.9$ in Fig. S2c,d, respectively.

These simulations are performed only at the ZPL wavelength and with the emitter positioned at the center of the nanopillar. While a real V2 defect emits over a broader spectrum and may reside at different locations within the

pillar, exploring these additional configurations lies beyond the scope of this work. The present model is therefore intended as a representative estimate to guide the nanopillar geometry rather than an exhaustive optimization.

Supplementary Note 3. 2D-PL Before and after UV pulse

We perform 2D photoluminescence (PL) experiments on all nanopillars, followed by single UV pulse exposure, with varying pulse energy. Subsequently, we perform 2D PL scans again over the same nanopillars. The 2D-PL measurements are performed with a different objective than the one used for the UV pulse, and exchanging objectives leads to a small shift in collection efficiency. Therefore, in order to have a fair comparison between the before- and after-scans, we use the mean count rate of a reference bulk region (grey dashed line in S3) to establish a common baseline and extract the appropriate scaling factor between the two measurements. We use $\alpha = \sqrt{\mu_{\text{before}} \times \mu_{\text{after}}}$ (with μ the mean along the dashed grey line) and define the scaling factor for before and after as $\beta_{\text{before,after}} = \frac{\mu_{\text{before,after}}}{\alpha}$. We multiply all the counts in the before- and after-scans by β_{before} and β_{after} , respectively. Note that more nanopillars were exposed to a UV pulse than the ~24 visible in each 2D-PL scan, and not all scans are included in this supplement. The scans shown are taken at approximately the same X–Y positions, although the exact center positions before and after exposure do not perfectly coincide.

At pulse energies of 0.16 μJ and above, we observe a clear increase in PL across multiple nanopillars, marking the onset of light-emitting defect formation. As the LIAT is approached, all nanopillars exhibit a substantial PL enhancement, suggesting the formation of additional emitters or non-visible (with SEM inspection) amorphization.

Figure S3. **Normalised 2D PL before and after a single UV pulse for different pulse energies.** Here, the factor β is indicated in each 2D PL scan. The dashed grey line indicates the Y location, which is used to normalise the before- and after-PL counts with respect to each other.

Supplementary Note 4. Room-temperature laser saturation

At room temperature, we performed PL measurements on all UV-exposed nanopillars (100 nanopillars per pulse energy). For each nanopillar, we first optimize the objective position by applying 500 μW of off-resonant laser power and scan all 3 axis of the objective. Afterwards, we extract the PL counts at the optimal position and plot the distribution of maximum PL counts versus pulse energy in a violin plot Fig. S4. We observe that the level of PL counts and spread increases for pulse energies $\geq 0.18 \mu\text{J}$. Next, we sweep the off-resonant laser power from 0 mW to 2 mW and collect the PL (example in main text Fig. 1f). We fit the data to a saturation curve (PL from defect) + a linear term (background PL):

$$PL = B \cdot p + A \cdot \frac{p}{p + p_{\text{sat}}}. \quad (\text{S3})$$

Figure S4. **Distribution Photoluminescence:** Maximum PL signal after scanning X, Y and Z axis of the objective with an off-resonant laser power of 500 μJ . The violin plot displays the distribution (symmetric histogram) for each UV pulse energy.

Here, p indicates the off-resonant laser power and B , A and p_{sat} are fitting parameters. We then define ρ at p_{sat} as $\frac{A_{\text{sat}}}{A_{\text{sat}} + B_{\text{sat}}}$, with $A_{\text{sat}} = \frac{A}{2}$ and $B_{\text{sat}} = B \cdot p_{\text{sat}}$ which gives us the ratio between the signal and the background PL. We plot the distribution of ρ at p_{sat} for each UV pulse energy in the violin plots displayed in Fig. S5. We observe a decrease in the lower tail of the distribution ($\rho \leq 0.6$) for an increase in UV pulse energy. Furthermore, we notice a slight increase of ρ at p_{sat} and a small decrease in variance for pulse energies $\geq 0.16 \mu\text{J}$. However, there is also a slight decrease in ρ for pulse energies $\geq 0.24 \mu\text{J}$, hinting at an increase in background fluorescence.

Figure S5. **Signal vs. background (ρ) at saturation power.** Violin plot distribution of the fraction between the amplitude of the saturating signal vs the background signal at fitted saturation power.

Supplementary Note 5. Location of V2 centers

To count the number of V2 centers, we perform PLE measurements on each nanopillar according to the scheme indicated in the inset of Fig. 2a. The method is explained in the methods section of the main text. In Fig. S6, Fig. S7, Fig. S8, we show the spatial location and fitted PLE data for the unexposed, 0.18 μJ , and 0.24 μJ nanopillars, respectively, which hosts ‘bright V2 centers’ passing the threshold. There seems to be no direct relationship between the spatial location of the nanopillars and the number of ‘bright V2 centers’. All nanopillars are within $\sim 50 \mu\text{m}$ of the bondwire, and for each group of 64 nanopillars, the optical path was optimized on collection efficiency. Furthermore, the nanopillars shown in this section are all located within an area of $250 \mu\text{m} \times 20 \mu\text{m}$.

All PLE spectra for nanopillars that contain V2 centers and did not pass the threshold can be found in Fig. S9, Fig. S10, Fig. S11

Figure S6. **Photoluminescence excitation of 64 unexposed nanopillars.** The white circles indicate a raster of nanopillars. The grey circles indicate nanopillars with V2 centers passing the 0.3 kHz threshold (grey dashed line), and their respective PLEs are shown below. Note that for all the PLE figures the relative laser frequency was scanned from -30 GHz to 30 GHz (offset is 327.112 THz)

Figure S7. **Photoluminescence excitation of 64 nanopillars exposed to a single pulse of $0.18\ \mu\text{J}$.** The white circles indicate a raster of nanopillars. The blue circles indicate nanopillars with V2 centers passing the $0.3\ \text{kHz}$ threshold (grey dashed line), and their respective PLEs are shown below. Note that for all the PLE figures the relative laser frequency was scanned from $-30\ \text{GHz}$ to $30\ \text{GHz}$ (offset is $327.112\ \text{THz}$)

Figure S8. **Photoluminescence excitation of 64 nanopillars exposed to a single pulse of 0.24 μ J.** The white circles indicate a raster of nanopillars. The blue circles indicate nanopillars with V2 centers passing the 0.3 kHz threshold (grey dashed line), and their respective PLEs are shown below. Note that for all the PLE figures the relative laser frequency was scanned from -30 GHz to 30 GHz (offset is 327.112 THz)

Figure S9. **Photoluminescence excitation of 64 unexposed nanopillars.** The white circles indicate a raster of nanopillars. The grey circles indicate nanopillars with V2 centers passing the 0.3 kHz threshold (grey dashed line), and their respective PLEs are shown below. Note that for all the PLE figures the relative laser frequency was scanned from -30 GHz to 30 GHz (offset is 327.112 THz)

Figure S10. **Photoluminescence excitation of 64 nanopillars exposed to a single pulse of 0.18 μ J.** The white circles indicate a raster of nanopillars. The blue circles indicate pillars with V2 centers that did not pass the threshold, and their respective PLEs are shown below. Note that for all the PLE figures the relative laser frequency was scanned from -30 GHz (offset is 327.112 THz)

Figure S11. **Photoluminescence excitation of 64 nanopillars exposed to a single pulse of 0.24 μJ .** The white circles indicate a raster of nanopillars. The blue circles indicate pillars with V2 centers that did not pass the threshold, and their respective PLEs are shown below. Note that for all the PLE figures the relative laser frequency was scanned from -30 GHz to 30 GHz (offset is 327.112 THz)

Supplementary Note 6. Spectral diffusion rate

To measure the spectral diffusion rate, we employ the scheme shown in Supplementary Note 6. Here, we keep both resonant lasers on during the *X-block*, and we use the no-recapture model to fit the data²³. For off-resonant diffusion, we apply the off-resonant laser during the *X-block* and fit the data to the diffusion-only model²³. The no-recapture

Figure S12. **Spectral diffusion measurement scheme.** Experimental sequence. A ‘check’ block (2 ms, 20 nW) is followed by a system perturbation (marked ‘X’), which here consists either of turning on the NIR lasers or turning on the off-resonant laser. A second block (2 ms, 20 nW) probes whether the defect has diffused away, or has ionised (denoted ‘probe’). Data is post-selected by imposing a minimum-counts threshold (T), heralding the emitter on resonance in the first (second) block and computing the mean number of counts in the second (first) block, which encodes the emitter brightness at future (past) delay times t . To measure spectral diffusion under resonant excitation, we use two resonant lasers, each at 20 nW. For spectral diffusion under off-resonant laser light, we use an off-resonant laser (785 nm with 10 μ W).

model fits the data as:

$$C(t)/C_0 = \begin{cases} (1 + \gamma_d t / \Gamma)^{-1} e^{-\gamma_d t}, & \text{if } t > 0. \\ (1 - \gamma_d t / \Gamma)^{-1}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{S4})$$

And the diffusion-only model fits the data as:

$$C(t)/C_0 = \begin{cases} (1 + \gamma_d t / \Gamma)^{-1}, & \text{if } t > 0. \\ (1 - \gamma_d t / \Gamma)^{-1}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (\text{S5})$$

For both models, the spectral diffusion rate γ_d depends on the linewidth of the specific V2 center of interest. We assume that the linewidth is not lifetime-limited, and thus, if we want to extract the diffusion rate, we need to measure the homogeneous linewidth of each V2. Since we did not measure the homogenous linewidth for each V2 center, we take a range for γ_d where:

$$\gamma_d = \gamma_{d,\text{lifetime}} \frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma_{\text{lifetime}}}. \quad (\text{S6})$$

Here, Γ is the homogeneous linewidth of the emitter while $\gamma_{d,\text{lifetime}}$ is the spectral diffusion rate assuming a lifetime-limited linewidth: Γ_{lifetime} . We take a maximum diffusion rate for $\Gamma = 3 \cdot \Gamma_{\text{lifetime}}$ (see Supplementary Note 7).

Supplementary Note 7. Bayesian analysis for Check-Probe PLE

We perform the check-probe PLE around the $A1$ transition to determine the homogeneous linewidths of several V2 centers in the nanopillars of Fig. 3a,b. The pulse sequence for the check-probe ple is shown in Fig. S13. This type of ple allows to measure the homogeneous linewidths in systems where the rate of spectral diffusion is relatively high. Since the check and probe blocks are short (2 ms) compared to the rate of spectral diffusion under resonant excitation.

Figure S13. **Check-probe ple scheme.** An off-resonant laser pulse (10 μ s and 10 μ W) is applied followed by two resonant laser pulses (both 2 ms and 20 nW) together with microwaves (127 MHz) to avoid spinpumping. The first resonant block acts as a check (effective initialisation) and the second resonant block acts as a probe (readout). The two blocks are separated by a waiting time of 5 μ s.

The probe spectrum obtained from this sequence typically contains some residual inhomogeneous broadening due to imperfect initialisation in the check step. To account for this, we analyse the data using the Bayesian framework introduced in van de Stolpe *et al.*²³ (Supplementary Note 4). Within this model the mean number counts from the probe block at a frequency detuning f is expressed as the convolution of the spectral probability density (i.e. the residual inhomogeneous broadening) and the intrinsic emitter spectral response $\lambda(f)$:

$$C(f) = P(f | m \geq T) * \lambda(f), \quad (\text{S7})$$

where the spectral probability density function is given by

$$P(f | m \geq T) = \frac{1}{N_T} (1 - \Gamma_i [T, \lambda(f - f_1)]), \quad (\text{S8})$$

with $\lambda(f)$ the expected mean number of counts during obtained in a single check block when the emitter is at frequency f and the laser at frequency f_1 . The function Γ_i denotes the incomplete Gamma function

$$\Gamma_i[a, z] = \frac{1}{\Gamma_c[a]} \int_z^\infty t^{a-1} e^{-t} dt \quad (\text{S9})$$

with $\Gamma_c[a]$ the Euler-Gamma function. The emitters intrinsic spectral response is a Lorentzian described as

$$\lambda_L(f) = C_0 \frac{\left(\frac{\Gamma}{2}\right)^2}{f^2 + \left(\frac{\Gamma}{2}\right)^2}. \quad (\text{S10})$$

Because both terms in Equation S7 depend on $\lambda(f)$, the apparent spectral response varies with the set threshold T from the check-block. And thus by increasing T the amount of residual broadening becomes negligible. By fitting Equation S7 to the data where we sweep the threshold, we can extract the homogeneous linewidth Γ and C_0 . An example of the fit is shown in Fig. S14.

Threshold sweeps were performed for several natural V2 centers (Fig. S15) and laser-induced V2 centers (single 0.18 μ J pulse in Fig. S16 and single 0.24 μ J pulse in Fig. S17). The resulting linewidths are compared to the lifetime-limited value of ~ 26 MHz for the $A1$ transition. Note that due to the initialisation in the check-block with a single laser and a microwaves we also have a small probability to initialise in the $\pm \frac{3}{2}$ subspace. This introduces a small probability of measuring the $A2$ transition which has a longer lifetime and can therefore result in an lower the measured Γ .

For measured two V2 natural V2 centers (different ones from Supplementary Note 5 and observe linewidths $\sim 2 \cdot \Gamma_{\text{lifetime}}$. This indicates that we still have some residual inhomogeneous broadening and/or power broadening

effects. Since the measurements were highly automatized, the count rate was not optimised perfectly before each measurement and can influence the spectral density function (thresholding) significantly. Laser-induced V2 centers exhibit comparable $\frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma_{\text{lifetime}}}$ and thus show that the linewidth is not significantly broadened for laser-induced V2 centers and close to the lifetime limit. A more precise determination of the homogeneous linewidth, including Rabi-induced broadening, could be obtained with a low magnetic field (~ 0 G) and high microwave power, so that Landau-Zener-Stückelberg interference becomes observable. These experiments lie beyond the scope of this study.

Figure S14. **Example of fitting check-probe signal.** **a)** Data obtained from pillar 21 (Fig. S8) where the threshold is swept from 1 to 17. **b)** Fitted convolution of Equation S7 to the data. **c)** Flattened data of a) and b) where the x axis is flattened and normalised. From the fit we extract $\Gamma = 39.0(4)$ MHz and $C_0 = 7.42(6)$

Figure S15. Γ for 2 natural V2 centers. **a)** Data of check-probe ple where threshold is swept for two V2 centers. Which were not in Fig. S6 but a different place. **b)** Extracted Γ from fitting a) compared to Γ_{lifetime} for the same pillars. The dashed line indicates the lifetime limited Γ . **c)** Extracted C_0 from fitting a).

Figure S16. Γ for several laser-induced V2 centers using UV pulse energy of $0.18\mu\text{J}$. **a)** Data of check-probe ple where threshold is swept for six V2 centers. **b)** Extracted Γ from fitting a) compared to $\Gamma_{lifetime}$ for the same pillars. The dashed line indicates the lifetime limited Γ . **c)** Extracted C_0 from fitting a).

Figure S17. Γ for several laser-induced V2 centers using UV pulse energy of $0.24\mu\text{J}$. **a)** Data of check-probe ple where threshold is swept for six V2 centers. The V2 in pillar X is a V2 center which did not pass the set threshold from Fig. 2. **b)** Extracted Γ from fitting a) compared to $\Gamma_{lifetime}$ for the same pillars. The dashed line indicates the lifetime limited Γ . **c)** Extracted C_0 from fitting a).

Supplementary Note 8. Optical properties of other laser-induced V2 center

For the measurements on the spin properties, we use one of the brightest V2 centers (pillar 8 Fig. S7). This V2 center also has a relatively low spectral diffusion rate under off-resonant excitation. In Fig. S18 we show the diffusion rates under off-resonant and resonant excitation, together with a scanning PLE and check-probe PLE. We observe a slightly larger linewidth ($\sim 2 \cdot \Gamma_{\text{lifetime}}$ see Supplementary Note 7) and slightly faster spectral diffusion rate compared to the V2 center in the main text.

Figure S18. **Emitter optical properties and laser-induced charge dynamics of V2 used for spin coherence measurements.** **a)** Fitted spectral diffusion constant under offresonant excitation for natural V2 centers (circles) and laser-induced V2 centers (squares and triangles, 0.18 μJ and 0.24 μJ respectively). The error bars indicate error in fit, the shaded region indicates the γ_d interval for $1 \leq \Gamma/\Gamma_{\text{lifetime}} \leq 3$ (see Supplementary Note 6). γ_d is extracted using methodology described in van de Stolpe *et al.*²³. γ_d of the red square indicates the same V2 center as the green square in b) and data in c), d), e) and f). **b)** Fitted spectral diffusion constants under resonant excitation for the same V2 centers as in a). **c)** Data and fit to extract γ_{diff} under off-resonant excitation. **d)** Data and fit to extract γ_{diff} under resonant excitation. **e)** Scanning laser PLE over 5 minutes. The laser is on for a total of 334 ms per scan. We conditionally apply an off-resonant pulse if a single scan gives less than 5 counts. This is done to counter ionisation (several scans show no counts or only a single optical transition). **f)** Check-Probe PLE (see van de Stolpe *et al.*²³ for methodology) indicating a near-lifetime limited optical linewidth, performed at a magnetic field of ~ 20 G

To confirm we are solely addressing a single V2 center we perform a g^2 -correlation measurement. We apply limited off-resonant power (1 μW to avoid ionisation and reduce background counts) and two resonant lasers at the frequency of the A1 and A2 transition (both 20 nW and collect data for 20 min)

Figure S19. **g^2 -correlation measurement under resonant excitation.** We apply limited off-resonant power (1 μW to avoid ionisation and reduce background counts) and two resonant lasers at the frequency of the A1 and A2 transition (both 20 nW and collect data for 20 min). The data for $g^2(0) = 0.175$ indicates that this is indeed a single V2 center that we can address resonantly.

Supplementary Note 9. Electron spin measurements

Figure S20. **Pulse schemes for spin measurements.** **a)** A framework of pulse sequences shared by Rabi, electron spin resonance (ESR), Ramsey, Hahn echo, and dynamical decoupling (DD) measurements is reported in the main text. R represents a 785 nm repump laser, f_1 a laser resonant with the A1 transition, f_2 a laser resonant with the A2 transition, and MW_M some parametrized microwave sequence that depends on the specific measurement and the parameter M . In each measurement, we run the entire laser and microwave sequence M times, sweeping the parameter M for the MW sequence, and we repeat the sweep N times to mitigate errors such as shot noise. **b)** In Rabi measurements, we fix the frequency and power of MW driving and sweep its duration t_M . **c)** In ESR, we send a MW π -pulse for fixed duration and power and sweep its frequency f_M . **d)** In Ramsey measurements, we sweep MW sequences of the form $(\frac{\pi}{2} - \tau_M - \frac{\pi}{2})$, where $\pi/2$ represents a MW $\pi/2$ -pulse with fixed duration, frequency and power and τ_M represents the variable interpulse delay. **e)** In Hahn echo measurements, we sweep MW sequences of the form $(\frac{\pi}{2} - \tau_M - \pi - \tau_M - \frac{\pi}{2})$, with $\frac{\pi}{2}$, π and τ_M similarly defined. **f) g)** In DD measurements, we run XY4 and XY8 sequences and sweep the interpulse delay $2\tau_M$. $\frac{\pi}{2}_X$ and $\frac{\pi}{2}_{-X}$ represent MW $\frac{\pi}{2}$ pulses with a phase of 0° and 180° respectively, and π_X and π_Y represent MW π pulses with a phase of 0° and 90° respectively,

To investigate the electron spin properties of laser-induced V2 centers, we perform Rabi oscillation, electron spin resonance (ESR), Ramsey, Hahn echo and dynamical decoupling (DD) measurements on pillars 9 and 14 (Fig. S7). The pulse sequences for all experiments are summarized in Fig. S20. We begin by resetting the spin environment of the V2 center with a $10 \mu\text{s}$ 785 nm laser pulse in the **repump** block. Then, we verify that the V2 center is on resonance by illuminating both resonant lasers for $150 \mu\text{s}$ in the **check** block. Subsequently, we populate the $m_s = \pm \frac{3}{2}$ subspace by exciting the A1 transition for $60 \mu\text{s}$ in the spin-pump (**sp**) block. This is followed by two identical normalization blocks (**norm.1** and **norm.0**), each exciting the A2 transition for $60 \mu\text{s}$. Photon counts are recorded in both blocks. We then apply appropriate microwave pulse sequences to run different measurements in the MW_M block, before reading out the population in $m_s = \pm \frac{3}{2}$ subspace with a $60 \mu\text{s}$ A2 laser pulse in the readout (**ro**) block. A wait time of $10 \mu\text{s}$ is inserted between adjacent blocks.

We apply a threshold on the photon count rates recorded during the **check** block. For those repetitions that pass the threshold, we calculate the mean of photon counts during **norm.1**, **norm.0** and **ro** blocks, denoted as A , B and C respectively, as well as the unbiased estimators of standard deviations σ_A , σ_B and σ_C . The normalized readout R

Figure S21. **Measured and simulated Rabi Chevron patterns of Pillar 9.** Solid dark lines in each panel correspond to resonant frequencies fitted in the DESR spectrum (Fig. 4b in main text). **a)** Measured data, also displayed in Fig. 4a. **b)** Simulated with the hyperfine coupling extracted from the DESR spectrum.

is then calculated as

$$R = \frac{C - B}{A - B}, \quad (\text{S11})$$

and the uncertainty σ_R is propagated as

$$\sigma_R = \sqrt{\frac{(C - B)^2}{(A - B)^4} \sigma_A^2 + \frac{(A - C)^2}{(A - B)^4} \sigma_B^2 + \frac{1}{(A - B)^2} \sigma_C^2}. \quad (\text{S12})$$

In ESR measurements, we fit the normalized readout R to 2 Gaussian peaks with a shared full-width at half-maximum (FWHM). We then extract a T_2^* using

$$T_{2,\text{DESR}}^* = \frac{2\sqrt{\ln 2}}{\pi \cdot \text{FWHM}}. \quad (\text{S13})$$

In detuned Ramsey measurements, we fit the normalized readout R to the following function:

$$R = b + e^{-(\tau/T_2^*)^2} \sum_i A_i \cos \left[\left(f_c + \frac{(-1)^i}{2} f_{\text{HF}} \right) \tau + \varphi_i \right], \quad (\text{S14})$$

where τ is the interpulse delay, $i = 0, 1$ labels the peaks fitted in the DESR spectrum, A_i and φ_i are the amplitude and phase of the oscillation due to detuning from each DESR peak, f_c is the center or average frequency of all oscillations, f_{HF} is the hyperfine coupling of the nuclear spin, b is a global offset and T_2^* is the extracted dephasing time. For the fit in the main text (Fig. 4c) we extract $f_c = 2.13(3)$ MHz.

In Hahn echo measurements, we fit the normalized readout R to a stretched decay function:

$$R = b + A e^{-(t/T_2)^n}, \quad (\text{S15})$$

where $t = 2\tau$ is the total time the V2 electron spin is allowed to dephase on the xy -plane of the Bloch sphere, τ is the interpulse delay, A is the amplitude of the decay, b is a global offset, T_2 is the extracted coherence time and n is the decay exponent.

In DD experiments, we fit the same stretched decay function. Here, we have $t = 2N\tau$ where N is the number of decoupling π pulses and 2τ is the wait time between two successive π pulses.

Supplementary Note 10. Spin coherence of V2 center in pillar 14 at low magnetic field

We also characterised the spin properties of the highlighted V2 center in Fig. 3 (pillar 14 Fig. S7). For this V2 center, we could not find a (resolvable) strongly coupled nuclear spin. See Fig. S22a,b for the Rabi chevron pattern and ESR measurement. We find a similar spin coherence time $T_2^* = 0.9(1) \mu\text{s}$ (see Fig. S22c) as the V2 center shown in Fig. 4.

Figure S22. **Spin measurements at low field of V2 center in pillar 14:** a) Rabi chevron pattern. Details on the measurement sequence and normalisation procedure are elaborated in Supplementary Note 9. b) Electron-spin-resonance of V2 center revealing no strongly coupled nuclear spin. c) Resonant Ramsey measurement on the same V2 center with $f_{MW} = 1814.8 \text{ MHz}$. Red line indicates a fit to a Gaussian decay with $T_2^* = 0.9(1) \mu\text{s}$.

Supplementary Note 11. Optical setups

For this work, we used 2 confocal setups, one at both ambient pressure and temperature, and one cryogenic setup (4K).

a. Ambient-temperature setup

We couple an 785 nm off-resonant laser (Cobolt 06-MLD785) to free space using a zoom fiber collimator (Thorlabs, ZC618APC). Free Space: The collimated beam passes through a variable neutral density filter (ND, Thorlabs NDC-50C-4-B), after which a $\lambda/2$ - $\lambda/4$ waveplate combination allows for polarisation control. The excitation path and detection path are separated with a 925 nm dichroic beamsplitter (Semrock FF925-Di01-25x36). We use a nanosecond-pulsed nitrogen laser (LaserTechnik Berlin MNL 100) which delivers 3 ns pulses at 337.1 nm. We control the energy of the UV pulses using a neutral density filter on a servo motor (coarse) and the laser's voltage (fine). We measure the pulse energy just before the objective using a μ -Joule Meter (PEM 250, LaserTechnik Berlin). Using a 355 dichroic beamsplitter (Semrock, Di01-R355-25x36) we align the UV laser to the sample. A flip mirror and 50/50 pellicle beamsplitter (Thorlabs, BP150) enable imaging of the sample with a visible LED (MCWHL6-C2) and a CCD-camera (ClearView Imaging, BFS-U3-16S2M-CS). Two different objectives are used to focus the laser onto the sample: a 60X, 0.7 NA (Olympus LUCPLFLN60X) and a 100 \times , 0.9 NA objective ([137]). The 60X, 0.7 NA objective is employed for laser writing because of its compatibility with UV wavelengths. For room-temperature defect

characterization, we use the 100X, 0.9 NA objective, which offers improved photon collection, but does not support UV transmission. The objective can be moved using a configuration of 3 piezo-electric stages (PI Q545.140). Collected fluorescence passes through both dichroic beamsplitters and is filtered with an 830 nm long-pass filter (Semrock, BLP01-830R-25) and collected in a fiber. We perform the 2D-PL measurements without a 50/50 beamsplitter, but for the saturation measurements, we used a 50/50 beamsplitter as we also performed g^2 -correlation measurements. We use two single-photon superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs, Single Quantum) with over 90% detection efficiency at 917 nm. The coarse time scheduling (1 s resolution) of the experiments is managed by a microcontroller (ADwin Pro II)

Figure S23. **Room-temperature confocal optical setup.** Details in text above the figure.

b. Low-temperature optical setup

The low-temperature optical setup is divided into two parts, in-fiber (left) and free-space (right). The electronics are not depicted in the figure.

In Fiber: Two NIR lasers (916 nm, Toptica DL Pro and the Spectra-Physics Velocity TLB-6718-P, are frequency-locked to a wavemeter (HF-Angstrom WS/U-10U), using a 99/1 beamsplitter. Their optical power is modulated by acousto-optic modulators (AOM, G&H SF05958). The power of the 785 nm repump laser (Cobolt 06-MLD785) is directly controlled via analog modulation. A wavelength division multiplexer (WDM, OZ Optics) combines the 785 nm repump and 916 nm NIR laser light, after which the light is coupled out to free space using a zoom fiber collimator (Thorlabs, ZC618APC).

Free Space: The collimated beam passes through a variable neutral density filter (ND, Thorlabs NDC-50C-4-B), after which a shortpass filter at an angle (Semrock, FF01-945/SP-25) is used to remove any residual noise from the NIR lasers. A $\frac{\lambda}{2} - \frac{\lambda}{4}$ waveplate combination allows for polarisation control. The excitation and detection paths are separated by a broadband 90:10 beamsplitter (Thorlabs, BS041). We use a fast-steering mirror (Newport, FSM-300-02) and a 4f system to scan the lasers over the sample. A flip mirror and 50/50 pellicle beamsplitter (Thorlabs,

BP150) enable imaging of the sample with a visible LED (MCWHL6-C2) and a CCD-camera (ClearView Imaging, BFS-U3-16S2M-CS).

A 0.9 NA microscope objective (Olympus, MPLFLN 100X) is used to focus excitation light onto the nanopillars and to collect fluorescence. The objective is kept at room temperature and under vacuum, and is moved (coarse) using a configuration of 3 piezo-electric stages (PI Q545.140). The sample is cooled down to 4K in a closed-cycle cryostat (Montana Instruments S100), while a heat shield kept at 30K limits thermal radiation from the objective.

Collected fluorescence passes through a 90/10 beamsplitter, after which it can be routed either to a spectrometer (Princeton Instruments IsoPlane 81), filtered with an 830 nm long-pass filter (Semrock, BLP01-830R-25), or to the single photon superconducting nanowire single-photon detectors (SNSPDs, Single Quantum) with over 90% detection efficiency at 917 nm. Next to a 830 nm long pass filter, an additional long-pass filter (Semrock, FF01-937/LP-25), placed at an angle, is used to filter out reflected light originating from the NIR lasers (916 nm).

Electronics: Microwave pulses are generated with an arbitrary waveform generator (Zurich Instruments, HDAWG8) and subsequently amplified (Mini-circuits LZY-22+). A bondwire is spanned across the sample to deliver the MW radiation close to the sample surface ($\sim 25 \mu\text{m}$). The coarse-time scheduling ($1 \mu\text{s}$ resolution) of the experiments is handled by a microcontroller (ADwin Pro II).

Figure S24. **Low-temperature confocal optical setup.** Details in text above the figure.